

Fact Sheet for researchers

Virtual Research Environments in Agroecology Transition: Insights and Applications from the ALL-Ready Project

Summary

- Virtual Research Environments (VREs) are rapidly becoming a cornerstone in science, streamlining research processes and fostering collaboration.
- VREs are digital platforms in the form of a website designed to provide seamless access to all services a data user needs to do data-related work and collaborate with the community to create new knowledge.
- The All-Ready Agroecology VRE simplifies, centralize, digitalize and streamline the creation of interdisciplinary innovation ecosystems and communities via collaboration between Agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures.
- The All-Ready Agroecology VRE catalyse change towards agroecology transition by providing users the opportunity to be inspired by others' ideas and innovations, learn by sharing and get advice from experts to build research solutions targeted to specific needs

Virtual Research Environment conceptual scheme. Generated with Bing Bing AI. 17 October 2023

Problem

Unsustainable agricultural practices, combined with the impacts of climate change, jeopardize food security and environmental sustainability.

Agroecology offers a remedy by applying ecological principles in agriculture management, however its adoption remains very low. The transition to more sustainable farming practices is hindered by some factors,

such as insufficient and scattered data and knowledge on agroecosystems management and the absence of harmonised mechanisms and tools that allow sharing of results, experiences and best practices.

Solution

Through the ALL-Ready project, there's an endeavour to foster a transition towards agroecology by leveraging VRE as a digital tool to facilitate harmonized data management and sharing experiences and results between members of Agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures. During the project, members of the Pilot Network of Agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures have co-designed an Agroecology VRE that standardizes collaboration for research an innovation among Agroecology stakeholders. It simplifies, centralize, digitalize and streamline the creation of interdisciplinary innovation ecosystems and communities via collaboration with complementary partners that match their needs. The proposed Agroecology VRE aim to enhance collaboration, streamline research processes, and expedite the transition to sustainable agroecological practices, addressing both environmental and food security challenges.

Benefits

Embracing Virtual Research Environments in the realm of agroecology promises a paradigm shift in how we approach sustainable farming. These platforms pave the way for centralized access to a vast array of data and research results, fostering data-sharing and informed decision-making and innovation. With a VRE, collaborative efforts become seamless, bringing together diverse expertise from various regions to tackle pressing challenges. Enhanced data analytics within VREs provide predictive insights, guiding farmers towards optimal practices, while also promoting educational outreach. This might lead to not only increased yield and reduced resource wastage, but also to the conservation of biodiversity. As a result, ecosystems flourish, local communities benefit, and the agricultural sector moves closer to a holistic balance with nature, ensuring long-term resilience.

VREs revolutionize agroecology, fostering collaboration, addressing challenges, and driving sustainable agricultural and environmental advancements through informed decisions

Research needs/Main results

The ALL-Ready project's Agroecology VRE is a groundbreaking web platform promoting standardized collaboration among diverse agroecology stakeholders. Streamlining the creation of interdisciplinary ecosystems, it ensures virtual collaboration with perfectly aligned partners. With functionalities like a marketplace, networking tools, and a resource repository, it guarantees effective knowledge sharing. Additionally, it offers geographical visualization of innovative ecosystems and advanced data management.

Designed to encompass a broad spectrum of users – from researchers to public bodies – it serves as a hub for agroecological knowledge exchange. The platform not only fosters connection but provides expert advice tailored to specific needs. By creating an environment for agroecological discussions and shared learning, it drives innovation. Through this VRE, the ALL-Ready Project bridges research needs with tangible agroecological outcomes.

The current version of the Agroecology VRE:

- Provide access to an interdisciplinary team for connecting and collaborating to move towards agroecology transition.
- Facilitate support and advice from experts to build strong solutions to specific needs, through collaboration.
- Facilitate discussion about Agroecology issues, learning by sharing.

Contribute to knowledge sharing and inspiration.

Practical recommendations

Main recommendations

Virtual Research Environments revolutionize agroecology by fostering multi-actor and multidisciplinary collaboration. These digital platforms enable real-time sharing of expertise, data, and best practices among different stakeholders worldwide. Through VREs, cutting-edge tools and analyses converge, allowing the implementation of eco-friendly farming techniques. This collaborative effort accelerates the agroecological transition, ensuring sustainable agriculture that harmonizes with nature, promoting food security and environmental preservation. For optimal utilization of the Agroecology VRE, stakeholders should actively engage in its diverse features.

Set up your detailed profile, start using all the functionalities provided and attract complementary partners.

Utilize the marketplace not just for transactions, but as a space for ideation and knowledge sharing.

Regularly update and share research findings in the repository, ensuring that innovations are accessible to all.

Engage in networking tools to foster interdisciplinary collaborations.

Leverage geographical visualizations to identify and connect with nearby innovation ecosystems.

By adhering to these guidelines, the platform's full potential can be unlocked, advancing agroecological transitions effectively.

Further information

FURTHER READINGS

- Ávila, J.M., Caro, D., González-Aranda, J.M. (2023) D6.4. Two training workshops for VRE use and technical follow-up & upgrading. ALL-Ready Project.
- Candela, L., Castelli, D., & Pagano, P. (2013). Virtual research environments: an overview and a research agenda. Data Science Journal, GRDI-013
- Other ALL-Ready project deliverables can be found here: <https://www.all-ready-project.eu/communication/deliverables.html>

WEBLINKS

- <https://www.all-ready-project.eu/virtual-research-environment.html> ALL-Ready Agroecology Virtual Research Environment

About ALL-Ready: ALL-Ready is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) funded by the European Commission (EC) with the aim of preparing a framework for a future European network of Living Labs (LL) and Research Infrastructures (IR) that will enable the transition towards agroecology throughout Europe. Based on the premise that agroecology can strengthen the sustainability and resilience of farming systems, the project will contribute to addressing the multiple challenges that they are facing today including climate change, loss of biodiversity, dwindling resources, degradation of soil and water quality.

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